

Embedding of Octonion Fourier Transform in Geometric Algebra of \mathbb{R}^3 and Polar Representations of Octonion Analytic Signals*

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Abstract. We show how the octonion Fourier transform can be embedded and studied in Clifford geometric algebra of three-dimensional Euclidean space $Cl(3,0)$. We apply a new form of dimensionally minimal embedding of octonions in geometric algebra, that expresses octonion multiplication non-associativity with a sum of up to four (individually associative) geometric algebra product terms. This approach leads to new polar representations of octonion analytic signals.

Keywords: Clifford geometric algebra · octonions · Fourier transform · analytic signal · polar representation

1 Introduction

Hypercomplex Fourier transforms experienced rapid development during the last 30 years. A historical overview of this field can be found in [3], a variety of approaches is included in [7], and a recent comprehensive textbook is [8]. For a recent survey of signal and image processing in Clifford geometric algebra, see Section 6 of [10]. In Definition 9 of [4] a Clifford algebra based hypercomplex Fourier transform producing a multidimensional analytic signal was defined. In the book [5] this approach is applied for the non-associative and non-commutative hypercomplex algebra of octonions. Apart from its non-associativity, octonions have many outstanding algebraic properties (e.g. the highest dimensional normed division algebra). It is therefore of great interest for us in this work to use a recently invented minimal embedding [11, 12] of octonions in the Clifford geometric algebra of three-dimensional space $Cl(3,0)$ and consequently embed the octonion Fourier transformation (OFT) in $Cl(3,0)$. This embedding allows to break down non-associative octonion multiplication into sums of associative geometric products, and therefore to easily apply existing geometric algebra computing software [1, 2, 15]. And it allows to establish new polar representations for octonion analytic signals.

* Soli Deo Gloria. Dedicated to the 44,821 Europeans who died due to Covid-19 vaccine adverse drug reactions, as of 21 May 2022 [17].

We first review in Section 2 the properties of octonions [13] and in Section 3 the new embedding of octonions in Clifford geometric algebra $Cl(3,0)$. Then we present in Section 4 the OFT of [5], as well as octonion analytic signals, and in Section 5 embed the OFT in $Cl(3,0)$. Finally, in Section 6 we utilize the polar decomposition of [9, 16] for complex biquaternions and multivectors in $Cl(3,0)$ to introduce new polar representations for octonion analytic signals.

2 Octonions

Here we first briefly summarize important octonion algebra properties (see [13], pp. 300–302, and [11]), assuming $a, b, c, x, y \in \mathbb{O}$.

- Octonions \mathbb{O} form an eight-dimensional bilinear algebra over the reals \mathbb{R} with basis $\{1, \mathbf{e}_1, \mathbf{e}_2, \mathbf{e}_3, \mathbf{e}_4, \mathbf{e}_5, \mathbf{e}_6, \mathbf{e}_7\}$.
- The multiplication table¹ is given by $(1 \leq i, j \leq 7)$

$$\mathbf{e}_i \star \mathbf{e}_i = -1, \quad \mathbf{e}_i \star \mathbf{e}_j = -\mathbf{e}_j \star \mathbf{e}_i \text{ for } i \neq j, \quad \mathbf{e}_i \star \mathbf{e}_{i+1} = \mathbf{e}_{i+3}, \quad (1)$$

where $(i, i+1, i+3)$ can be permuted cyclically and translated modulo 7.

- Via the Cayley-Dickson doubling process, octonions can directly be defined from pairs of quaternions $p_1, p_2, q_1, q_2 \in \mathbb{H}$ (note the order of factors, $\text{qc}(\dots)$ is quaternion conjugation):

$$(p_1, q_1) \star (p_2, q_2) = (p_1 p_2 - \text{qc}(q_2) q_1, q_2 p_1 + q_1 \text{qc}(p_2)). \quad (2)$$

- \mathbb{O} has no zero divisors, i.e., $ab = 0$ implies $a = 0$ or $b = 0$.
- \mathbb{O} is a division algebra, i.e., $ax = b$ and $ya = b$ have unique solutions x, y for non-zero a .
- \mathbb{O} admits unique inverses.
- \mathbb{O} is non-associative, i.e., in general $a(bc) \neq (ab)c$.
- \mathbb{O} is alternative, i.e., $a(ab) = a^2 b$ and $(ab)b = ab^2$.
- \mathbb{O} is one of only four alternative division algebras over \mathbb{R} : $\mathbb{R}, \mathbb{C}, \mathbb{H}, \mathbb{O}$.
- \mathbb{O} is flexible, i.e., $a(ba) = (ab)a$.
- \mathbb{O} has a (positive-definite quadratic form) norm $\|\dots\| : \mathbb{O} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, the norm is preserved (i.e. admits composition), such that $\|ab\| = \|a\| \|b\|$.
- \mathbb{O} is one of only four unital norm-preserving division algebras over \mathbb{R} : $\mathbb{R}, \mathbb{C}, \mathbb{H}, \mathbb{O}$.
- \mathbb{O} is essential for treating *triality*, an automorphism of the universal covering spin group $\text{Spin}(8)$ of the rotation group $\text{SO}(8)$ or \mathbb{R}^8 . Triality is not an inner automorphism, nor an orthogonal matrix similarity, nor a linear transformation $Cl(8,0) \rightarrow Cl(8,0)$, nor a linear automorphism of $\text{SO}(8)$. Triality permutes three elements in the center of $Cl(8,0)$, namely $\{-1, e_{12345678}, -e_{12345678}\}$, with basis vectors e_i , $(1 \leq i \leq 8)$, of \mathbb{R}^8 . Triality is a restriction of a polynomial mapping $Cl(8,0) \rightarrow Cl(8,0)$ of degree two.

Furthermore, like for complex numbers, quaternions and biquaternions, there is a *polar decomposition* for octonions [16].

¹ This depends obviously on deliberate ordering and sign choices for the basis elements.

3 Embedding of Octonions in Clifford Geometric Algebra of Three-Dimensional Euclidean Space

For readers not familiar with Clifford geometric algebra we refer to the excellent textbook [13], and to the tutorial introduction [6]. The current section summarizes the results needed from [11].

The Clifford geometric algebra $Cl(3, 0)$ of Euclidean space \mathbb{R}^3 has eight basis elements

$$\{1, \sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3, I\sigma_1 = \sigma_{23}, I\sigma_2 = \sigma_{31}, I\sigma_3 = \sigma_{12}, I = \sigma_{123}\}, \quad (3)$$

where $\{\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3\}$ forms an orthonormal vector basis of \mathbb{R}^3 . We can construct in $Cl(3, 0)$ an octonionic product [11], after splitting it in its even subalgebra $Cl^+(3, 0)$ with basis

$$\{1, \sigma_{23}, \sigma_{31}, \sigma_{12}\}, \quad (4)$$

and the set $Cl^-(3, 0)$ of odd grade (w.r.t. grades in $Cl(3, 0)$) elements

$$\{\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3, I = \sigma_{123}\}. \quad (5)$$

We will use the Clifford conjugation² (indicated by an overbar $\overline{}$), i.e. the composition of (main) grade involution (\widetilde{M}) and reversion (\widetilde{M}), which preserves grades zero and three, but changes the signs of grades one and two in $Cl(3, 0)$. A realization of the octonionic product of M, N in $Cl(3, 0)$ is given by four geometric algebra product terms

$$\begin{aligned} M &= M_+ + M_-, & N &= N_+ + N_-, \\ M \star N &= M_+ N_+ + \overline{N_-} M_- + N_- M_+ + M_- \overline{N_+}, \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

with even grade parts $M_+, N_+ \in Cl^+(3, 0)$ and odd grade parts $M_-, N_- \in Cl^-(3, 0)$. The multiplication table is Table 1, with octonionic product illustration in Fano plane diagram form in Fig. 1.

The octonion conjugate (anti-involution) in $Cl(3, 0)$ is given by

$$M^* = \widetilde{M}_+ - M_- = \overline{M}_+ - M_-, \quad (M \star N)^* = N^* \star M^*. \quad (7)$$

Computing the octonion norm yields (including norm-preservation):

$$\|M\| = M \star M^* = \langle M \widetilde{M} \rangle = M * \widetilde{M} = \sum_{i=1}^8 M_i^2, \quad \|M \star N\| = \|M\| \|N\|. \quad (8)$$

where $M_i \in \mathbb{R}, 1 \leq i \leq 8$, are the coefficients of M in the $Cl(3, 0)$ basis (3).

The above reviewed embedding is very flexible. It even allows to reversely embed Clifford geometric algebra $Cl(3, 0)$ in octonions by defining the geometric product in terms of the octonionic product (see [11], Section 3.3 for details):

$$\begin{aligned} M_+ N_+ &\stackrel{(6)}{=} M_+ \star N_+, & M_- N_- &\stackrel{(6)}{=} N_- \star \overline{M}_-, \\ M_- N_+ &\stackrel{(6)}{=} N_+ \star M_-, & M_+ N_- &= -(N_- \star I) \star (M_+ \star I). \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

² Note that by construction $\overline{M_\pm} = (\overline{M})_\pm$.

Table 1. Multiplication table for octonion embedding in $Cl(3, 0)$. The upper left 4×4 -block corresponds to M_+N_+ , the upper right 4×4 -block to N_-M_+ , the lower left 4×4 -block to $M_-\bar{N}_+$, and the lower right 4×4 -block to \bar{M}_-N_- of (6).

Left factors	Right factors							
	1	$I\sigma_1$	$I\sigma_2$	$I\sigma_3$	σ_1	σ_2	σ_3	I
1	1	$I\sigma_1$	$I\sigma_2$	$I\sigma_3$	σ_1	σ_2	σ_3	I
$I\sigma_1$	$I\sigma_1$	-1	$-I\sigma_3$	$I\sigma_2$	I	σ_3	$-\sigma_2$	$-\sigma_1$
$I\sigma_2$	$I\sigma_2$	$I\sigma_3$	-1	$-I\sigma_1$	$-\sigma_3$	I	σ_1	$-\sigma_2$
$I\sigma_3$	$I\sigma_3$	$-I\sigma_2$	$I\sigma_1$	-1	σ_2	$-\sigma_1$	I	$-\sigma_3$
σ_1	σ_1	$-I$	σ_3	$-\sigma_2$	-1	$I\sigma_3$	$-I\sigma_2$	$I\sigma_1$
σ_2	σ_2	$-\sigma_3$	$-I$	σ_1	$-I\sigma_3$	-1	$I\sigma_1$	$I\sigma_2$
σ_3	σ_3	σ_2	$-\sigma_1$	$-I$	$I\sigma_2$	$-I\sigma_1$	-1	$I\sigma_3$
I	I	σ_1	σ_2	σ_3	$-I\sigma_1$	$-I\sigma_2$	$-I\sigma_3$	-1

4 Octonion Fourier Transform

From now on, if no brackets are given, the order of multiplication is assumed to be from left to right. According to Section 4.2.1 of [5], the OFT of an integrable real signal $f \in L^1(\mathbb{R}^3, \mathbb{R})$ can be defined as

$$\mathcal{F}\{f\}(\mathbf{u}) = \int_{\mathbb{R}^3} f(\mathbf{x}) e^{-\mathbf{e}_1 2\pi u_1 x_1} e^{-\mathbf{e}_2 2\pi u_2 x_2} e^{-\mathbf{e}_4 2\pi u_3 x_3} d^3x, \quad (10)$$

with three-dimensional position- and frequency vectors, and volume element

$$\mathbf{x} = (x_1, x_2, x_3) \in \mathbb{R}^3, \quad \mathbf{u} = (u_1, u_2, u_3) \in \mathbb{R}^3, \quad d^3x = dx_1 dx_2 dx_3, \quad (11)$$

respectively, and octonion units $\{\mathbf{e}_1, \mathbf{e}_2, \mathbf{e}_4\}$ in the exponents. As pointed out in [5], any triplet of octonion units could be used in the octonionic kernel of (10), as long as the three do not form a quaternionic subalgebra, by that reason, e.g., the triplet $\{\mathbf{e}_1, \mathbf{e}_2, \mathbf{e}_3\}$ is excluded, compare the multiplication table Table 2.3 and its Fano plane visualization Fig. 2.2 in [5]. In the latter the triplet $\{\mathbf{e}_1, \mathbf{e}_2, \mathbf{e}_3\}$ clearly lies on a straight line.

Given suitable integrability conditions, the inverse OFT can be computed as

$$f(\mathbf{x}) = \mathcal{F}^{-1}\{\mathcal{F}\{f\}\}(\mathbf{x}) = \int_{\mathbb{R}^3} \mathcal{F}\{f\}(\mathbf{u}) e^{\mathbf{e}_4 2\pi u_3 x_3} e^{\mathbf{e}_2 2\pi u_2 x_2} e^{\mathbf{e}_1 2\pi u_1 x_1} d^3u, \quad (12)$$

$$d^3u = du_1 du_2 du_3.$$

Abbreviating $s_k = \sin(2\pi u_k x_k)$, $c_k = \cos(2\pi u_k x_k)$, $k = 1, 2, 3$, we can express the kernel of (10), using multiplication table Table 2.3 of [5], as

$$\begin{aligned} e^{-\mathbf{e}_1 2\pi u_1 x_1} e^{-\mathbf{e}_2 2\pi u_2 x_2} e^{-\mathbf{e}_4 2\pi u_3 x_3} &= (c_1 - s_1 \mathbf{e}_1)(c_2 - s_2 \mathbf{e}_2)(c_3 - s_3 \mathbf{e}_4) \\ &= c_1 c_2 c_3 - s_1 c_2 c_3 \mathbf{e}_1 - c_1 s_2 c_3 \mathbf{e}_2 - c_1 c_2 s_3 \mathbf{e}_4 \\ &\quad + s_1 s_2 c_3 \mathbf{e}_3 + s_1 c_2 s_3 \mathbf{e}_5 + c_1 s_2 s_3 \mathbf{e}_6 - s_1 s_2 s_3 \mathbf{e}_7. \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Fig. 1. Illustration of $Cl(3,0)$ basis elements under the octonionic product (6) in Table 1, see [11] for details.

The significance of this decomposition is, that therefore a real signal $f \in L^1(\mathbb{R}^3, \mathbb{R})$ is decomposed by the OFT (10) into eight spectral components of distinct even-odd symmetries: $\{eee, oee, eoe, eeo, ooe, oeo, eoo, ooo\}$, where e=even, o=odd. Following the multiplication table Table 2.3 of [5], and using the alternative octonion multiplication property of Section 2, we find the following conjugations ($i, j = 2, \dots, 7$)

$$\alpha_i(\mathbf{e}_j) = \mathbf{e}_i \mathbf{e}_j \mathbf{e}_i = \begin{cases} \mathbf{e}_j, & i \neq j \\ -\mathbf{e}_j, & i = j \end{cases}. \quad (14)$$

This allows to express all $\mathcal{F}\{f\}(\pm u_1, \pm u_2, \pm u_3)$ in terms of $\mathcal{F}\{f\}(\mathbf{u})$ each time using four suitable α_i conjugations. For example,

$$\mathcal{F}\{f\}(-u_1, u_2, u_3) = \alpha_1(\alpha_3(\alpha_5(\alpha_7(\mathcal{F}\{f\}(\mathbf{u}))))). \quad (15)$$

As a consequence the OFT in all eight octants of the three-dimensional frequency space can be obtained from the OFT only applied to the first octant, where all three frequency components are positive (i.e. $\{u_1 \geq 0, u_2 \geq 0, u_3 \geq 0\}$).

4.1 Hypercomplex Analytic Signal

A real signal $f \in L^1(\mathbb{R}, \mathbb{R})$ can be extended to a complex analytic signal with *positive* frequency by multiplying its Fourier transform $\mathcal{F}_{\mathbb{R}}\{f\}(u)$ with $(1 + \text{sgn } u)$, $u \in \mathbb{R}$ being the frequency, and back transforming

$$\psi(x) = \mathcal{F}_{\mathbb{R}}^{-1}\{(1 + \text{sgn } u)\mathcal{F}_{\mathbb{R}}\{f\}(u)\}(x), \quad (16)$$

equivalent to application of the Hilbert transform, where \otimes means convolution,

$$H[f(x)] = \left(\frac{1}{\pi x}\right) \otimes f(x), \quad \psi(x) = f(x) + iH[f(x)] = \left[\delta(x) + i\frac{1}{\pi x}\right] \otimes f(x). \quad (17)$$

We can recover the original signal as the real part of $\psi(x)$, i.e.,

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{2}(\psi(x) + cc(\psi(x))). \quad (18)$$

Analogously, we can construct for real three-dimensional signals $f \in L^1(\mathbb{R}^3, \mathbb{R})$ an analytic hypercomplex signal with triple convolution by (see Section 5.2.3 of [5] for details)

$$\begin{aligned} \psi(x_1, x_2, x_3)_1 &= [\delta(x_1) + \mathbf{e}_1 \frac{1}{\pi x_1}] \times [\delta(x_2) + \mathbf{e}_2 \frac{1}{\pi x_2}] \times [\delta(x_3) + \mathbf{e}_4 \frac{1}{\pi x_3}] \\ &\quad \otimes \otimes \otimes f(x_1, x_2, x_3) \\ &= f + v_1 \mathbf{e}_1 + v_2 \mathbf{e}_2 + v_{12} \mathbf{e}_3 + v_3 \mathbf{e}_4 + v_{13} \mathbf{e}_5 + v_{23} \mathbf{e}_6 + v \mathbf{e}_7, \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

which has only three-dimensional frequency values $\mathbf{u} = (u_1, u_2, u_3)$ in the first octant of frequency space, where all three frequency components are positive $(+++)$. The original signal $f \in L^1(\mathbb{R}^3, \mathbb{R})$ is the scalar real component of $\psi(x_1, x_2, x_3)$. The corresponding analytic signals $\psi(x_1, x_2, x_3)_k$, $k = 2, \dots, 8$ in the other seven octants are obtained by simply changing the three plus signs in (19) to $(-++)$, $(+-+)$, $(- - +)$, $(+ + -)$, $(- + -)$, $(+ - -)$, $(- - -)$, respectively. And we can recover the original signal simply by

$$f(x_1, x_2, x_3) = \frac{1}{8} \sum_{k=1}^8 \psi(x_1, x_2, x_3)_k. \quad (20)$$

Instead of computing $\psi(x_1, x_2, x_3)_k$, $k = 2, \dots, 8$, one by one, we can obviously also obtain them from $\psi(x_1, x_2, x_3)_1$ by applying to it compositions of octonionic conjugations (14) as, e.g., in (15). We note that [5], p. 167, states for $\psi(x_1, x_2, x_3)_1$ of (19): *The exact polar representation of this signal is unknown.*

This outline of the OFT and its corresponding analytic first octant frequency spectrum signal may suffice here to be able to somewhat appreciate its uniquely interesting properties, due to its octonionic kernel. For more details we refer to [5].

5 Embedding the OFT in Clifford Geometric Algebra of Three-Dimensional Euclidean Space

Now we reach the main purpose of this work to extend the embedding of octonions in Clifford geometric algebra $Cl(3, 0)$ of Section 3 to a full embedding of the OFT. An essential first step is the question on how to identify the three unit octonions $\mathbf{e}_1, \mathbf{e}_2$, and \mathbf{e}_4 with corresponding non-scalar basis elements of $Cl(3, 0)$. In [5], page 70, when defining the OFT, it is emphasized that the choice of $\mathbf{e}_1, \mathbf{e}_2$, and \mathbf{e}_4 , for constructing the transformation kernel is not unique, but other triplets suggested always include \mathbf{e}_2 , located at the center of the Fano diagram Fig. 2.2 in [5]. Comparing this situation with our Fano diagram Fig. 1, we conveniently choose the three basis blades $\sigma_1, -I, -I\sigma_3$. We observe that

$\sigma_1, -I \in Cl^-(3, 0)$ are both odd-, and $-I\sigma_3 \in Cl^+(3, 0)$ is even graded, respectively.

We therefore define the embedding in the geometric algebra $Cl(3, 0)$ of the OFT of a real signal $f \in L^1(\mathbb{R}^3, \mathbb{R})$ as

$$\mathcal{F}\{f\}(\mathbf{u}) = \int_{\mathbb{R}^3} f(\mathbf{x}) e^{-\sigma_1 2\pi u_1 x_1} \star e^{I 2\pi u_2 x_2} \star e^{I \sigma_3 2\pi u_3 x_3} d^3 x. \quad (21)$$

The kernel of the embedded OFT can be expressed in geometric algebra, using multiplication table Table 1, as

$$\begin{aligned} K &= [e^{-\sigma_1 2\pi u_1 x_1} \star e^{I 2\pi u_2 x_2}] \star e^{I \sigma_3 2\pi u_3 x_3} \\ &= [(c_1 - \sigma_1 s_1) \star (c_2 + I s_2)] \star (c_3 + I \sigma_3 s_3) \\ &= c_1 c_2 c_3 - s_1 c_2 c_3 \sigma_1 + c_1 s_2 c_3 I + c_1 c_2 s_3 I \sigma_3 - s_1 s_2 c_3 \sigma_1 \star I - s_1 c_2 s_3 \sigma_1 \star (I \sigma_3) \\ &\quad + c_1 s_2 s_3 I \star (I \sigma_3) - s_1 s_2 s_3 [\sigma_1 \star I] \star (I \sigma_3) \\ &= c_1 c_2 c_3 - s_1 c_2 c_3 \sigma_1 + c_1 s_2 c_3 I + c_1 c_2 s_3 I \sigma_3 - s_1 s_2 c_3 I \sigma_1 + s_1 c_2 s_3 \sigma_2 \\ &\quad + c_1 s_2 s_3 \sigma_3 - s_1 s_2 s_3 I \sigma_2 \\ &= c_1 c_3 (c_2 + s_2 I) - s_1 c_3 (c_2 + s_2 I) \sigma_1 + s_1 s_3 (c_2 - s_2 I) \sigma_2 + c_1 s_3 (c_2 - s_2 I) I \sigma_3 \\ &= c_3 (c_1 - s_1 \sigma_1) (c_2 + s_2 I) + s_3 (s_1 \sigma_2 + c_1 \sigma_1 \sigma_2) (c_2 - s_2 I) \\ &= c_3 (c_1 - s_1 \sigma_1) (c_2 + s_2 I) + s_3 \sigma_1 \sigma_2 (c_1 - s_1 \sigma_1) (c_2 - s_2 I) \\ &= [c_3 (c_2 + s_2 I) + s_3 \sigma_1 \sigma_2 (c_2 - s_2 I)] (c_1 - s_1 \sigma_1) \\ &= [c_3 e^{I 2\pi u_2 x_2} + s_3 I \sigma_3 e^{-I 2\pi u_2 x_2}] (c_1 - s_1 \sigma_1) \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

New we observe that to change the sign of any of the three frequency components in the result, GA has very simple involutions

$$\begin{aligned} K(-u_1, u_2, u_3) &= \sigma_3 K(u_1, u_2, u_3) \sigma_3, & K(u_1, -u_2, u_3) &= \sigma_3 \widehat{K}(u_1, u_2, u_3) \sigma_3, \\ K(u_1, u_2, -u_3) &= \sigma_1 K(u_1, u_2, u_3) \sigma_1, & K(-u_1, -u_2, u_3) &= \widehat{K}(u_1, u_2, u_3), \\ K(-u_1, u_2, -u_3) &= \sigma_2 K(u_1, u_2, u_3) \sigma_2, & K(u_1, -u_2, -u_3) &= \sigma_2 \widehat{K}(u_1, u_2, u_3) \sigma_2, \\ K(-u_1, -u_2, -u_3) &= \sigma_1 \widehat{K}(u_1, u_2, u_3) \sigma_1, \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

with grade involution \widehat{K} that changes the sign of all odd grade parts. Note that the frequency sign change only operating in octonion algebra always requires a composition of *four* conjugations (as e.g. in (15)).

5.1 Embedding of Octonion Analytic Signal in Geometric Algebra $Cl(3, 0)$

We now ask how the octonion analytic signal, defined in (19), can be embedded in the geometric algebra $Cl(3, 0)$ of three-dimensional Euclidean space \mathbb{R}^3 ? Similar to our study of the kernel of the embedding of the OFT, we therefore need to apply the embedding of octonion multiplication in geometric algebra to the convolution factor product that appears in the definition of the octonion analytic

signal (19). We again replace $\mathbf{e}_1, \mathbf{e}_2$, and \mathbf{e}_4 , by the three $Cl(3, 0)$ basis blades $\sigma_1, -I$, and $-I\sigma_3$, and obtain³

$$\begin{aligned} & \{[\delta(x_1) + \sigma_1 \frac{1}{\pi x_1}] \star [\delta(x_2) - I \frac{1}{\pi x_2}]\} \star [\delta(x_3) - I\sigma_3 \frac{1}{\pi x_3}] \\ &= [\delta(x_3)(\delta(x_2) - I \frac{1}{\pi x_2}) - I\sigma_3 \frac{1}{\pi x_3} (\delta(x_2) + I \frac{1}{\pi x_2})] (\delta(x_1) + \sigma_1 \frac{1}{\pi x_1}). \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

The following threefold convolution, carried out algebraically in the geometric algebra $Cl(3, 0)$, will therefore give the embedding of the octonion analytic signal of (19) in $Cl(3, 0)$

$$\begin{aligned} \psi(x_1, x_2, x_3)_1 &= [\delta(x_3)(\delta(x_2) - I \frac{1}{\pi x_2}) - I\sigma_3 \frac{1}{\pi x_3} (\delta(x_2) + I \frac{1}{\pi x_2})] \\ &\quad (\delta(x_1) + \sigma_1 \frac{1}{\pi x_1}) \otimes \otimes \otimes f(x_1, x_2, x_3) \\ &= f + v_1\sigma_1 - v_2I - v_3I\sigma_3 - v_{12}I\sigma_1 + v_{13}\sigma_2 + v_{23}\sigma_3 + vI\sigma_2. \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

Furthermore, the seven simple GA involutions of (23) will also analogously yield the embedded version of the octonion analytic signal for the other seven octants, which corresponds to changing one, two or all three signs of $\sigma_1, -I$, and $-I\sigma_3$, in (25):

$$\begin{aligned} \psi(x_1, x_2, x_3)_2 &= \sigma_3\psi(x_1, x_2, x_3)_1\sigma_3, & \psi(x_1, x_2, x_3)_3 &= \sigma_3\widehat{\psi}(x_1, x_2, x_3)_1\sigma_3, \\ \psi(x_1, x_2, x_3)_4 &= \widehat{\psi}(x_1, x_2, x_3)_1, & \psi(x_1, x_2, x_3)_5 &= \sigma_1\psi(x_1, x_2, x_3)_1\sigma_1, \\ \psi(x_1, x_2, x_3)_6 &= \sigma_2\psi(x_1, x_2, x_3)_1\sigma_2, & \psi(x_1, x_2, x_3)_7 &= \sigma_2\widehat{\psi}(x_1, x_2, x_3)_1\sigma_2, \\ \psi(x_1, x_2, x_3)_8 &= \sigma_1\widehat{\psi}(x_1, x_2, x_3)_1\sigma_1, \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

where in number ordering of the octants we simply follow Fig. 4.10 and Table 5.4 of [5]. The original scalar signal can always be reconstructed from the eight octant specific signals of (25) and (26), and therefore from the purely positive frequency (in the first octant of the three-dimensional frequency space) signal $\psi(x_1, x_2, x_3)_1$, as

$$f(x_1, x_2, x_3) = \frac{1}{8} \sum_{k=1}^8 \psi(x)_k, \quad (27)$$

which is the octant generalization of the reconstruction (18) of a real one-dimensional signal from its complex analytic signal. The single complex conjugation in (18) is replaced by the seven geometric algebra involutions of (26).

6 Polar Representation of Embedded Octonion Analytic Signal

As shown in [16], Theorem 1, there exists an elegant and very compact polar decomposition for complex biquaternions. Due to the isomorphism between com-

³ Note the close algebraic analogy to the computation in (22), associating c_k and $\delta(x_k)$, as well as s_k and $-1/(\pi x_k)$, for $k = 1, 2, 3$.

plex biquaternions and the Clifford algebra $Cl(3,0)$, this can be carried over to multivectors in $Cl(3,0)$ as well, see [9], Section 4.3, equation (49).

As for notation, unit vectors u (two degrees of freedom (DOF)), unit bivectors i_2 (two DOF), and the central unit pseudoscalar $I = \sigma_{123}$ in $Cl(3,0)$ square to

$$u^2 = +1, \quad i_2^2 = -1, \quad I^2 = -1. \quad (28)$$

The even subalgebra of $Cl(3,0)$ is *isomorphic to quaternions* \mathbb{H} : $Cl_2(3,0) \cong \mathbb{H}$. That means general multivectors M in $Cl(3,0)$ can always be represented as complex ($I^2 = -1$) (bi)quaternions:

$$M = M_+ + M_- = p + Iq, \quad (29)$$

where p and q are (isomorphic to) quaternions

$$p = M_+ = a_p e^{\alpha_p i_p}, \quad q = I^{-1} M_- = a_q e^{\alpha_q i_q}, \quad a_p, a_q \in \mathbb{R}_0^+, \quad i_p^2 = i_q^2 = -1, \quad (30)$$

with unit bivectors $i_p, i_q \in Cl_2(3,0)$.

The polar decomposition of $M \in Cl(3,0)$ is

$$M = p + Iq = \begin{cases} e^{\alpha_0} e^{\alpha_2 i_2} & \text{for } q = 0, \\ I e^{\alpha_0} e^{\alpha_2 i_2} & \text{for } p = 0, \\ e^{\alpha_0} e^{\alpha_2 i_2} \frac{1+I\mathbf{f}}{2} & \text{for } q = p\mathbf{f}, \\ e^{\alpha_0} e^{\alpha_1 u'} e^{\alpha_2 i_2} e^{\alpha_3 I} & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (31)$$

where in line three (compare (26) in [9]) we have the special case that the quotient $p^{-1}q$ results in a unit bivector $\mathbf{f} = p^{-1}q$. The value of $i_2 = i_p$ in lines one (compare (19) in [9]) and three, $i_2 = i_P$ in line four, while in line two we have $i_2 = i_q$. We note that line one is a special case of line four for $\alpha_1 = \alpha_3 = 0$. Line two (compare (19) in [9]) is a special case of line four for $\alpha_1 = 0$ and $\alpha_3 = \pi/2$. So essentially only lines three and four of (31) matter, and we have one special (line three) case with idempotent factor ($\frac{1+I\mathbf{f}}{2}$) and one general case (line four: see Section 4.2 of [9] for all computational details) with full exponential factorization. The latter has the necessary eight DOF: four DOF are given by the phase angles α_k , $k = 0, 1, 2, 3$, two DOF by unit vector u' and two by unit bivector i_2 .

To better understand how to compute the generic case decomposition of line four of (31), we present the following numerical example (see details in Appendix A).

Example 1.

$$\begin{aligned} M &= 1 + 2\sigma_1 + 3\sigma_2 + 4I\sigma_1 + 5I\sigma_3 + 6I = e^{1.0436} e^{1.5574 u'} e^{-0.66405 i_2} e^{1.8304 I}, \\ u' &= 0.9047\sigma_1 - 0.1544\sigma_2 + 0.3972\sigma_3, \\ i_2 &= 0.2959I\sigma_3 + 0.6685I\sigma_2 + 0.6823I\sigma_1. \end{aligned} \quad (32)$$

We thus propose to use this new polar representation method (31) for the embedded octonion analytic signal (25), is *one way to answer* the open question for the exact polar representation of (19).

Another way to answer this question can be proposed based on analysis of a separable three-dimensional signal $f(x_1, x_2, x_3) = g_1(x_1)g_2(x_2)g_3(x_3)$, $g_k \in L^1(\mathbb{R}^1, \mathbb{R}^1)$, $k = 1, 2, 3$, that leads to a decomposition of the form

$$\psi_1 = a_1 a_2 a_3 [\cos(\alpha_2) e^{-\alpha_3 I} - \sin(\alpha_2) I \sigma_3 e^{\alpha_3 I}] (\cos(\alpha_1) + \sin(\alpha_1) \sigma_1), \quad (33)$$

or more general

$$\psi_1 = A [\cos(\alpha_2) e^{-\alpha_3 I} + \sin(\alpha_2) i_2 e^{\alpha_3 I}] (\cos(\alpha_1) + \sin(\alpha_1) u), \quad (34)$$

with suitably defined amplitudes $a_k, A \in \mathbb{R}$, angles $\alpha_k \in \mathbb{R}$, $k = 1, 2, 3$, unit vector $u \in \mathbb{R}^3$, and unit bivector $i_2 \in Cl^2(3, 0)$.

Further research has to show which of these two ways may be preferable.

7 Conclusion

We have briefly reviewed octonions and their new minimal embedding in the geometric algebra of three-dimensional space $Cl(3, 0)$. We further reviewed the notion of OFT and octonion analytic signal, embedded both in $Cl(3, 0)$, and finally suggested two interesting possibilities for polar decompositions of the embedded octonion analytic signal. Further research, including concrete applications to non-separable signals, is desirable.

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A Computation of Example 1

The $Cl(3,0)$ multivector

$$M = 1 + 2\sigma_1 + 3\sigma_2 + 4I\sigma_1 + 5I\sigma_3 + 6I \quad (35)$$

has according to (30)

$$p = 1 + 4I\sigma_1 + 5I\sigma_3, \quad q = I^{-1}(2\sigma_1 + 3\sigma_2 + 6I) = 6 - 2I\sigma_1 - 3I\sigma_2. \quad (36)$$

A first step is to norm M by division with the square root of $M\overline{M}$.

$$\begin{aligned} M\overline{M} &= (1 + 2\sigma_1 + 3\sigma_2 + 4I\sigma_1 + 5I\sigma_3 + 6I)(1 - 2\sigma_1 - 3\sigma_2 - 4I\sigma_1 - 5I\sigma_3 + 6I) \\ &= 1 - 4 - 9 + 16 + 25 - 36 + I(12 - 16) = -7 - 4I \\ &= \sqrt{65} \frac{-7 - 4I}{\sqrt{65}} = e^{2 \times 1.0436} e^{2 \times 1.8304I}, \end{aligned} \quad (37)$$

showing that $\alpha_0 = 1.0436$ and $\alpha_3 = 1.8304$. We therefore have

$$\sqrt{M\bar{M}} = e^{1.0436} e^{1.8304I}, \quad (38)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} N &= M\sqrt{M\bar{M}}^{-1} = (p + Iq)e^{-1.0436}e^{-1.8304I} \\ &= 1.9519 + 1.1807\sigma_1 - 0.2712\sigma_2 + 1.7019\sigma_3 \\ &\quad - 0.4520I\sigma_3 - 1.0212I\sigma_2 - 1.0424I\sigma_1 - 0.8828I \\ &= N_+ + II^{-1}N_- = P + IQ. \end{aligned} \quad (39)$$

Therefore

$$\begin{aligned} P &= 1.9519 - 0.4520I\sigma_3 - 1.0212I\sigma_2 - 1.0424I\sigma_1, \\ Q &= -0.8828 - 1.1807I\sigma_1 + 0.2712I\sigma_2 - 1.7019I\sigma_3. \end{aligned} \quad (40)$$

And we represent P as a rotor

$$P = a_P e^{\alpha_P i_P} = 2.4786 e^{-0.66405 \times (0.2959I\sigma_3 + 0.6685I\sigma_2 + 0.6823I\sigma_1)}, \quad (41)$$

that is

$$\begin{aligned} a_P &= \sqrt{P\bar{P}} = 2.4786, \quad \alpha_2 = \alpha_P = -0.66405, \\ i_2 &= i_P = 0.2959I\sigma_3 + 0.6685I\sigma_2 + 0.6823I\sigma_1. \end{aligned} \quad (42)$$

We will soon need

$$a_Q = \sqrt{Q\bar{Q}} = 2.2679. \quad (43)$$

We finally have

$$e^{\alpha_1 u'} = NP^{-1} = Na_P^{-1} e^{-\alpha_P i_P} = 1 + 0.8278\sigma_1 - 0.1413\sigma_2 + 0.3634\sigma_3, \quad (44)$$

with unit vector part

$$u' = \frac{\langle NP^{-1} \rangle_1}{|\langle NP^{-1} \rangle_1|} = 0.9047\sigma_1 - 0.1544\sigma_2 + 0.3972\sigma_3, \quad (45)$$

and

$$\alpha_1 = \operatorname{atanh} \frac{a_Q}{a_P} = \operatorname{atanh} \frac{2.2679}{2.4786} = 1.5574. \quad (46)$$

In summary the polar decomposition gives

$$\begin{aligned} M &= e^{1.0436} e^{1.5574 u'} e^{-0.66405 i_2} e^{1.8304 I}, \\ u' &= 0.9047\sigma_1 - 0.1544\sigma_2 + 0.3972\sigma_3, \\ i_2 &= 0.2959I\sigma_3 + 0.6685I\sigma_2 + 0.6823I\sigma_1. \end{aligned} \quad (47)$$

All computations have been verified with The Clifford Multivector Toolbox for Matlab [15].

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